

2. R. M. SILVERSTEIN, G. C. BASSLER and T. C. MORRILL, "Spectrometric Identification of Organic Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1981.
3. N. B. COLTHUP, L. H. DALY and S. E. WIBERLY, "Introduction to Infrared and Raman Spectroscopy", Academic, New York, 1968.
4. B. N. BERAD, S. P. DESHMUKH and M. G. PARANJPE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, 61, 888.
5. V. B. KADU, M. Phil. Project, Nagpur University, 1984.
6. E. E. REID, "Organic Chemistry of Bivalent Sulphur", Chemical Publishing, New York, 1963, Vol. 5, p. 490.
7. G. OTTMAN and H. HOOK, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1966, 31, 838.

Terpenoids and Phenolics from the Bark and Heartwood of *Sterculia urens* Roxb.

A. S. R. ANJANEYULU* and S. NOOKA RAJU

School of Chemistry, Andhra University, Waltair-530 003

Manuscript received 30 January 1987, accepted 22 April 1987

STERCULIA urens Roxb. has been reputed for its medicinal use¹; gum in throat affections and leaves and tender branches for pleuro-pneumonia in cattle. We have reported² the isolation of a new C-methylchalcone, stercurensin from the leaves of *S. urens*. The results of the chemical examination of the bark and heartwood of *S. urens* are reported in this communication.

The air-dried and powdered bark (2 kg) of *S. urens* collected from an aged tree in the Punyagiri forests of Visakhapatnam, was extracted with methanol. The extract on concentration left β -sitosterol (Compound E, 0.2 g) which was identified by direct comparison (m.m.p., co-ir). The mother liquor after evaporation of the solvent under reduced pressure gave a residual gum (50 g) which was reextracted successively with n-hexane, chloroform and methanol. The residue (8 g) from the green hexane extract was chromatographed over a column of Si-gel to yield seven compounds: A (0.12 g, m.p. 79–80°), B (0.08 g, m.p. 107–08°), C (0.1 g, m.p. 115–16°), D (0.16 g, m.p. 204–05°), E (0.1 g, m.p. 136–37°) and F (0.1 g, m.p. 248–49°). The residue from the chloroform extract on column chromatography and elution with benzene-ethyl acetate (4:1) gave compound G (0.08 g). No crystalline compound was obtained from the methanol extract. Compounds A, B, C, D and F were identified as n-hexacosanol, cycloartenone, cycloartenol, lupeol and betulin, respectively, by comparison of their physical and spectral (ir, nmr) data and finally by direct comparison with the authentic samples (m.m.p., co-ir).

Compound G was crystallised from MeOH as brown prisms, m.p. 203–04° and analysed for $C_{10}H_8O_4$. It was recognised as a coumarin by its colour reactions³: yellow solution when heated with NaOH, and bright blue fluorescence of its methanolic solution under uv light. The ir peak at 1730 cm^{-1} and uv maxima at 342 and 294 nm further support its coumarin nature. It yielded a

monoacetate, m.p. 176–77°, and monomethyl ether, m.p. 144–50°. The characteristic 3-H and 4-H protons of coumarin appeared at δ 6.14 and 7.69 as doublets (J 9.5Hz) in its nmr spectrum in DMSO- d_6 in addition to an aromatic methoxyl at δ 3.88 and two aromatic protons as singlets at δ 6.80 and 6.98. A comparison of the above physical and spectral characteristics of compound G with those of scopoletin⁴, 7-hydroxy-6-methoxy-coumarin, proved their identity.

The air-dried and powdered heartwood of *S. urens* (5 kg) was successively extracted with n-hexane and alcohol. The residue from the hexane extract yielded 3 compounds: H (0.15 g, m.p. 84–5°), I (0.12 g, m.p. 118–20°) and J (0.1 g) in addition to cycloartenone (0.15 g), cycloartenol (0.1 g) and β -sitosterol (0.2 g) by column chromatography. The residue from the alcohol extract was further fractionated into ether and methanol solubles. The residue (35 g) obtained after evaporation of solvent from the ether extract was separated into phenolic and non-phenolic fractions by the usual treatment with basic lead acetate in methanol. The yellowish brown residue (8 g) from the phenolic fraction yielded compounds K (0.1 g), L (0.05 g) and scopoletin (0.04 g) by column chromatography.

Compounds H and I were identified as n-octacosanol and cycloartenyl acetate, respectively, by study of their physical characteristics and by direct comparison (m.m.p. and co-ir). Compound J was crystallised from $CHCl_3$ -MeOH as colourless needles, m.p. 136–37°, $[\alpha]_D +46^\circ$, $C_{30}H_{50}O$; ν_{max} 3500 (OH) and 890 cm^{-1} ($=CH_2$). It yielded a monoacetate, $C_{30}H_{52}O_2$, m.p. 150–51°, $[\alpha]_D +61.5^\circ$. The physical and spectral (ir and nmr) characteristics of compound J suggested that it might be identical with dammadienol (lit.⁵ m.p. 137°, $[\alpha]_D +47^\circ$; acetate m.p. 150–51°, $[\alpha]_D +61.5^\circ$) although a direct comparison with which could not be made.

Compound K was crystallised from MeOH as light yellow feathery needles, m.p. 206–07°, $[\alpha]_D -16.5^\circ$. It gave bright colour with Shinoda's reagent and red colour with $NaBH_4/HCl$ suggesting its flavanone nature. It was analysed for $C_{17}H_{16}O_5$, M^+ 300; showed the absorption peaks at ν_{max} (KBr) 3450 (OH) and 1640 cm^{-1} ($C=O$). A bathochromic shift of 40 nm in band II with NaOMe relative to its uv spectrum in MeOH indicated the presence of 5,7-dihydroxyl groups in K. It readily formed a diacetate, $C_{21}H_{20}O_7$, m.p. 168–70° with Ac_2O/Py and a dimethyl ether, $C_{19}H_{20}O_5$, m.p. 102° with ethereal diazomethane solution. These derivatives showed further hydroxylic ir absorption at 3250 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of 5-OH, which is supported by a D_2O -exchangeable proton at δ 11.86 in the nmr spectrum of its diacetate. With Ac_2O/CH_3COONa , compound K yielded a triacetate, $C_{23}H_{22}O_8$, m.p. 192°. The nmr spectrum of K in CD_3OD revealed the presence of characteristic flavanone protons at δ 5.25 (1H, d, J 11, 4Hz, C_8-H) and 2.80 (2H, m, C_9-2H). It further

showed the presence of two C-methyls at δ 1.99 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{Ar}-\text{CH}_3$) and the four protons (A_2B_2) of the paradisubstituted B-ring as the doublets at δ 6.79 (2H, d, 3'-H and 5'-H) and 7.29 (2H, d, 2'-H and 6'-H). The physical and spectral (uv, ir, nmr and ms) characteristics of compound K suggested it to be identical in all respects with those of farrerol⁶, 4',5,7-trihydroxy-6,8-dimethylflavanone.

Compound L was crystallised from MeOH as pale yellow feathery needles, m.p. 255–60°, $C_{20}H_{18}O_8$; ν_{max} –OH in its ir at 3450 cm^{-1} (OH); gave a diacetate with $\text{Ac}_2\text{O}/\text{Py}$, which was crystallised from MeOH as feathery needles, $C_{24}H_{22}O_{10}$, m.p. 168–69°, M^+ 470. Preliminary spectral studies indicated that it might belong to a novel class of compounds whose structural investigation is in progress.

The co-occurrence of different groups of triterpenes and phenolics such as coumarin and flavanone in this plant is of biogenetic significance. Besides, a C-methylflavonoid, farrerol is isolated for the first time from the plants of Sterculiaceae.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (S.N.R.) is grateful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for the award of Teacher Fellowship.

References

1. R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAYAR and I. C. CHOPRA, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", C. S. I. R., New Delhi, 1956, p. 234.
2. A. S. R. ANJANEYULU and S. NOOKA RAJU, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1984, **23**, 1010.
3. R. H. GOODWIN and F. KAVANAGH, *Arch. Biochem. Biophys.*, 1950, **27**, 152.
4. H. ROBERTSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1241.
5. A. COLLIN and ASSELINEAU, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.*, 1957, 1359.
6. J. B. HARBORNE and G. A. WILLIAMS, *Phytochemistry*, 1971, **10**, 2727.

Redox Titration with Manganese(IV) using 2-Nitrodiphenylamine as Indicator

U. MURALIKRISHNA*, K. SUBRAHMANYAM
and

J. ARUNACHALARAMANA

Department of Chemistry, Andhra University, Waltair-530 003

Manuscript received 3 July 1983, revised 3 April 1987,
accepted 19 May 1987

2-NITRODIPHENYLAMINE (NDA) is known to be a versatile and high potential (1.12 V) reversible redox indicator¹ in the titrimetric analysis with Ce^{IV} , Mn^{VII} and V^{V} . The use of NDA in the titrations with Mn^{IV} in sulphuric acid medium is reported in the present communication.

*Present address: A.U.P.G. Extension Centre, Nuzvid-521 201.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade. A 0.1 N standard arsenic(III) solution, and approximately 0.1 N solutions of iron(II), hydroquinone, hexacyanoferrate(II) and antimony(III) were prepared and standardised². A 0.1 N solution of manganese(IV) was prepared and standardised by the procedure of Mandal and Sant³. 0.01 M iodine-monochloride⁴ and 0.1% solution of NDA in acetic acid were also prepared.

General procedure: The prepared reductant solutions 10–25 ml were diluted to 100 ml maintaining appropriate acidity and were treated with NDA (0.2 ml) and finally titrated with a standard 0.1 N manganese(IV) solution till the colour sharply changed from yellow to red.

Satisfactory titrations could also be carried out with a 0.01 N solution of Mn^{IV} provided an indicator correction of 0.01 ml is applied for 0.2 ml of the indicator used.

Results and Discussion

The acidity conditions for the titrations were fairly wide: 1–5 M for iron(II), 1–6 M for hydroquinone, 1–3 M for arsenic(III) and 1–4 M for antimony(III). However, for hexacyanoferrate(II) 2 M acidity should be maintained. The colour change at the end-point was sharp for all the titrations but first appearance of red colour should be taken as the end-point in the case of hydroquinone. The reactions were sufficiently fast and no catalyst was required for iron(II), hexacyanoferrate(II) and hydroquinone. Small amount (1–3 ml) of 0.01 M iodine monochloride was required as catalyst for arsenic(III) and antimony(III) titrations. The accuracy of results were in the following range: 1–2 milliequivalents (meq.) of iron(II) (with a standard deviation of ± 0.01), 0.5–1.7 meq. of hydroquinone (± 0.02), 0.5–1 meq. of hexacyanoferrate(II) (± 0.01), 1–2 meq. of arsenic(III) (± 0.03), and 0.7–2 meq. of antimony(III) (± 0.02). The proposed method is convenient and is applicable even in dilute solutions.

Acknowledgement

Two of the authors (K.S. and J.A.R.) thank U.G.C., New Delhi, for the award of F.I.P. Fellowships and the management of Mrs. A. V. N. College, Visakhapatnam for deputation.

References

1. M. K. GANDIKOTA and G. G. RAO, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1970, **65**, 231, 1974, **72**, 163.
2. I. M. KOLTHOFF and R. BELCHER, "Volumetric Analysis", Interscience, New York, 1957, Vol. III, pp. 43, 177, 164, 53, 458.
3. S. K. MANDAL and B. R. SANT, *Talanta*, 1976, **23**, 485.
4. A. BERKA, J. VULPERIN and J. ZYKA, "Newer Redox Titrants", Pergamon, Oxford, 1965, p. 56.